

THE CYANINE DYES OF THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART IV.

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Four new cyanine dyes have been prepared by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with α -picoline-secondary-propyl, -secondary-butyl, -isobutyl, and -isoamyl iodides; and their chemical, optical, dyeing and photographic properties examined. The influence of change of structure on the sensitising power of these and other related compounds has also been discussed.

In previous communications of this series, the influence on the photographic, optical and general properties of the valuable photosensitising compound (P), by the change in Z (Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 347), in Y (Doja and Prasad, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 125), and in X (Doja and Prasad, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 377) have been described. Previously when

Y was changed, only straight-chained alkyl radicals were used; in the present paper, investigations and results are recorded in which Y has been replaced by branched chain alkyl radicals. Four different alkyl iodides, *e.g.* (1) secondary propyl, (2) secondary butyl, (3) *isobutyl*, and (4) *isoamyl* have been used for quaternising α -picoline. The quaternisation has been effected by heating equivalent quantities of the base and the alkyl iodide in a sealed tube in a boiling water-bath for 6 to 8 hours (*cf.* Murrill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 21, 828). In the case of the secondary-butyl iodide, the liquid reaction product had to be placed in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid for a fortnight before crystals of α -picoline-secondary-butyl iodide could be obtained. These quaternary compounds, when condensed with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in absolute alcohol (Mills and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2736), produced the new cyanine dyes. Comparatively speaking, the secondary-propyl-(A) and the secondary-butyl-(B) dyes are more difficult to prepare than the corresponding *isobutyl*-(C) and the *isoamyl*-(D) dyes. (B) could only be obtained in the crystalline state, after two reprecipitations of the alcoholic solution by ether, and subsequent recrystallisation of the mass from absolute alcohol. (A) too had to be slowly evaporated for a long period before it could be induced to crystallise. On the other hand, both (C) and (D) readily crystallised out from the reaction mixtures on cooling. The period of heating of the reactants was also smaller in the latter cases, it being 4 and 2 hours for (C) and (D) and 6 and 5 hours for (A) and (B) respectively.

TABLE I

Compound.	Structural difference.	Colour and shape of crystals.	M.p.	Reflex.	PLEOCHROISM One position. ⊥ position.		Relative intensity of colour in soln. Relative to resistance decolorisation.		Extra sensitisation. Range. Maximum.
A		Shining orange-red, felted small leaves	206-207°	Light yellow	Orange-brown	Weak yellow	1	1	5000-5750Å 5100Å
B		Deep magenta, tiny needle clusters	165.67°	Bluish-green	Rose-red	Orange-red	1.07	0.93	4900-5850Å 5050Å
C		Mauve, microscopic granular crystals	265°	Light green	Claret-red	Nearly opaque	1.69	1.30	4850-5750Å 5200Å
D		Vermilion, small granular crystals	246.47°	Sky blue	Ruby-red	Nearly opaque	1.28	1.18	4800-5950Å 5250Å

(A), (B), (C) and (D) refer respectively to 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine—secondary propyl iodide, secondary butyl iodide, isobutyl iodide, and isocamyl iodide.

Although α -picoline-secondary-propyl iodide and α -picoline-secondary-butyl iodide are both highly hygroscopic, the cyanine dyestuffs derived from them are not so.

The names, symbols, "distinguishing structural features," and some of the properties of these compounds are recorded in Table I. It will be noticed that in both (A) and (B), the quaternary nitrogen is attached to the secondary carbon atom of the alkyl radical, the two differing only in their size, (B) being one step higher in the homologous series than (A). The quaternary nitrogen atom in (C) is attached to a primary carbon situated next to the secondary carbon atom. In (D), the secondary carbon atom is farther removed, it being separated from the quaternary nitrogen by two intervening $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups.

When the melting points of the two pairs of compounds : [(A), (B)], and [(C), (D)] are compared, it is interesting to note that both (B) and (D), although possessing higher molecular weights than (A) and (C) respectively, have lower melting points.

The crystals of all the four compounds are lustrous and highly coloured ; their colour, " reflex " and " pleochroism," are given in Table I. They are soluble in common ionising solvents and insoluble in the non-ionising ones. Their colour in solution (1 : 10,000) is orange, the secondary dyes being slightly lighter than the *iso*-dyes. On concentration (1 : 1000) the solution becomes redder and on dilution (1 : 100,000), more yellow. The " Relative intensity " of 1 : 10,000 solutions in rectified spirit of these compounds colorimetrically determined, is given in Table I.

Like other cyanine dyes, the solutions of these compounds are decolorised by the addition of mineral acids. The amount of acid required for complete decolorisation varies with the nature of the dyestuff. For this series, the "Relative resistance to decolorisation" of alcoholic solutions (1 : 10,000) by dilute hydrochloric acid is shown in Table I.

It will be seen that the *isobutyl* dye (C) is most resistant to decolorisation, and the secondary butyl dye (B) least so.

Silk, cotton and wool are dyed by these compounds an orange-yellow colour, the different shades produced are tabulated in Table II. The best colour is obtained on silk. In the case of cotton, an acid bath gives a more pronounced reddish tinge than a neutral bath. Comparatively the most intense colour is produced by (C), and the weakest by (B). In view of the minor structural difference between (B) and (C), both being butyl compounds, this difference is remarkable. The gradation of the intensity of colour produced by the different compounds is in the following order :

Although very pretty to look at none of these shades is fast either to washing or to sunlight.

In Table III is recorded the fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions.

TABLE II

Colour produced on	Compound			
	A	B	C	D
Silk	Yellowish orange	Weak yellowish orange	Light orange	Orange yellow
Wool	Weak yellowish orange	Yellow	Orange	Yellowish orange
Cotton	Yellowish orange	Dirty orange	Deep orange	Deep orange

The colour on dilution (1 : 100,000) of these compounds was determined by a method described in an earlier communication (Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 348). The fluorescences, it will be noted, are very similar.

The sensitisation and absorption spectra of (A), (B), (C) and (D) are shown in Figure 1. The sensitisation spectra of all the four compounds are characterised by their high intensity, and the absence of the usual " gap " in the blue-green region of the spectrum. The *isoamyl* derivative (D), being the heaviest, has the longest extra-sensitisation band. The ranges and maxima of these sensitisation spectra are recorded in Table I.

When compared with the corresponding straight chain derivatives (Doja and Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 125), the sensitisation spectra of these compounds are

not very much different; which means that the introduction of branched alkyl radicals in place of Y in the compound (P) does not materially alter the sensitising power of the compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-secondary-propyl Iodide (A).—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (3 g.), α -picoline-secondary-propyl iodide (3.9 g.) and piperidine (1.0 c.c.), were dissolved in absolute alcohol (60 c.c.) and the solution boiled under reflux for 6 hours. The deep red solution was cooled, transferred to a crystallising dish, and slowly evaporated in a sulphuric acid vacuum desiccator for 6 hours. The separated crystals were recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, yield 1.2 g. (20.5%). (Found: I, 32.14. $C_{18}H_{23}N_2I$ requires I, 32.25 per cent).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-secondary-butyl Iodide (B).—A solution of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.), α -picoline-secondary-butyl iodide (3.1 g.) and piperidine (1.0 c.c.), in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), was gently boiled for 5 hours. The alcohol was evaporated off and the residual oily liquid again dissolved in alcohol and precipitated out with ether. After repeating this process twice, a semi-solid mass was obtained which yielded crystals after two recrystallisations from absolute alcohol, yield 1.25 g. (27.41%). (Found: I, 31.21. $C_{19}H_{25}N_2I$ requires I, 31.12 per cent).

TABLE III

Wallace colour Filter No.	Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam			
	A	B	C	D
1	Light completely absorbed	Light completely absorbed	Light completely absorbed	Light completely absorbed
2	Very weak cherry red	Weak red	Pink	Cherry red
3	Light brinjal blue	Weak blue	Sky blue	Weak blue
4	Very weak orange	Weak orange	Orange	Orange
5	Sulphur yellow	Lemon yellow	Turmeric yellow	Turmeric yellow
6	Weak greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Yellowish green
7	Grass green	Bottle green	Light green	Emerald
8	Brown	Brownish yellow	Brown	Brown
9	Dirty yellow (partly absorbed)	Dirty yellow	Weak dirty yellow	Weak dirty yellow
10	Dull yellow	Brownish yellow	Brownish yellow	Yellow

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-isobutyl Iodide (C).—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (2 g.), α -picoline-isobutyl iodide (3.6 g.) and piperidine (1 c.c.) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (35 c.c.) and the solution refluxed for 4 hours. The solution on cooling deposited crystals, which were recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, yield 1.04 g. (19.6%). (Found: I, 31.28. $C_{19}H_{25}N_2I$ requires I, 31.12 per cent).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-isoamyl Iodide (D).— α -Picoline-isoamyl iodide (2.8 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.5 g.), piperidine (1 c.c.) and absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), were heated together to a brisk boil for a couple of hours. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and the separated crystals were filtered, washed with alcohol-ether and recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield, 1.38 g. (33.4%). (Found: I, 30.16. $C_{20}H_{27}N_2I$ requires I, 30.08 per cent).